

**MULTIFACETED ANCILLARY FUNCTIONS AND WORK PERFORMANCES
AMONG PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOL TEACHERS
IN BULUAN DISTRICT**

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Multifaceted Ancillary Functions and Work Performances among Public Elementary School Teachers in Buluan District

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the different auxiliary functions affecting the productivity rate of public elementary school teachers in Buluan District, Division of Maguindanao-1, BARMM, Philippines. Using a descriptive-correlational research design, data from 102 teachers from nine schools were collected through a validated survey questionnaire. The study focused on the teachers' auxiliary roles, classified as curricular (i.e. lesson planning, coordination with community and research) and extra-curricular (i.e. coaching in sports, feeding programs and school canteen management), and their influence on the dimensions of work performance (instructional planning; involvement in professional growth and interaction with the community). The results of the study revealed that teachers have prominent functions, with a grand mean of 4.33 indicating their wide involvement in curricular and extra-curricular activities. Although the workload increased, teachers excelled in stated measures, explicitly instructional planning and community organizing. It was further established that for teachers, ancillary functions showed a significantly positive relationship with their work performance which means that the two variables are interlinked. The findings underscore the tensions between ancillary functions, which have been viewed as enhancing the professional skills of teachers and their involvement in their communities, and balancing the workload against instructional efficiency. Recommendations also advocated for the equitable sharing of ancillary functions, improved technical support from school heads, and recognition programs to motivate teachers and sustain high performance levels.

Keywords: *multifaceted ancillary function, work performance, curricular, extra-curricular*

Introduction

In the Department of Education (DepEd), a regular full-time teacher is compelled to dedicate a maximum of six hours each day to classroom instruction. This is stipulated under the Magna Carta for Public School Teachers. An employee needs to render eight (8) working hours every day. For public school teachers, the remaining two (2) hours will be allotted for lesson preparations, other teaching-related activities, and other ancillary assignments. An auxiliary function is a work that is necessary to the overall goals of how a system or organization operates (Salise et al. (2021). The term "ancillary functions" in the context of education refers to the tasks that teachers carry out that are not specifically related to teaching in the classroom, such as serving as class advisers, subject coordinators, club advisers, sports coaches, coordinators of both co-curricular and extracurricular activities, and community engagement services.

In in the Ministry of Basic Higher Technical Education (MBHTE) particularly, Buluan District, Division of Maguindanao-1, teachers are suffering from multifaceted ancillary functions mandatorily assigned by their heads. The effects of ancillary functions to the teaching performance of the teachers were inefficient instruction, absenteeism, and health problem and class interruption. They may also be experiencing sleep issues, such as excessive sleeping or worry-induced insomnia. They typically experience depression, overwhelm, or maybe just a loss of enjoyment (Clarion & Palarisan, 2023). Consequently, the reasons of the teachers of accepting multifaceted ancillary functions were professional growth, personal growth, obedience to supervisor, school head's trust and confidence, lastly professional responsibility. Above all, teachers with ancillary functions are having difficulties balancing their time.

As mentioned by Howard & Johnson (2004), multifaceted ancillary functions of teachers often lead towards losing their motivation, satisfaction, and competence, and even burning out.

In the study of Parham and Gordon (2011), combining multifaceted ancillary function emphasized positive impacts on an individual's well-being. Canadian teachers with multifaceted ancillary functions are reported to be less worn-out, stress-free, have high performance in their jobs, and with lower intentions to quit (Jamal, Baba, & Riviere, 1999; Yahya, Ismail, Salleh, & Abdullah, 2015). However in other countries, like Indonesia, ancillary services are integrated into schools to support the implementation of the first four national standards of education in relation to the overall national goal of education (Salise et al., 2021).

The study of Retubada (2014) mentioned that a multifaceted ancillary function of teachers is one of the problems encountered by schools in Davao Del Sur, Region XI. He cited that teachers, while performing their main function as classroom adviser, are also given extra non-teaching functions called ancillary functions as their additional workload since there is a need to assign these teachers as subject area coordinators, grade level head, canteen manager, sports coordinator, SBM, coordinator, club moderators, cluster subject area coordinator, coaches in different contests in cluster, division, regional and even at national levels which resulted into poor performance of teachers as well as students.

Although ancillary tasks are acknowledged to play a significant effect in determining teachers' career paths, limited empirical research

has been done to precisely look at how these diverse jobs affect public elementary school teachers' performance at work in Buluan District. Prior research, such that done by Parham and Gordon (2011), shows that pursuing supplementary roles only for advancement may have detrimental consequences for one's general well-being, job satisfaction, and work quality. Zickar, Gibby, and Jenny (2004) also highlight the difficulties of juggling a variety of positions, such as professional competition and the stress of juggling a wide range of duties.

But these studies mostly focus on general workplace situations and don't adequately represent the distinct experiences of teachers in public elementary education, especially in the Buluan District's organizational and cultural setting. Furthermore, the reasons for assuming supplementary responsibilities, their characteristics, and their particular impacts on teacher performance in this setting have all been intricately examined in the research that has already been written.

This study aims to address these gaps by providing localized insights into the relationship between multifaceted ancillary functions and work performance, offering a more comprehensive understanding of how these roles influence the professional effectiveness and satisfaction of teachers in public elementary schools.

Research Questions

This study was conducted to assess the extent of multifaceted ancillary functions and work performance of public elementary school teachers in Buluan District, Division of Maguindanao-1. Specifically, this answered the following research questions:

1. What is the extent of multifaceted ancillary functions of public elementary school teachers in Buluan District in terms of curricular and extra-curricular activities?
2. What is the level of work performance public elementary school teachers in Buluan District in terms of instructional planning, involvement in professional growth activities, interaction with administration and other educational personnel, interaction with parents and community, providing evaluative feedback, and supporting and implementing school regulations, policies, procedures and accepted practices?
3. Is there a significant relationship between multifaceted ancillary functions and performance of public elementary school teachers in Buluan District?

Literature Review

Ancillary Functions

According to Salise et al. (2021), an auxiliary function is a work that is necessary to the overall goals of how a system or organization operates. The term "ancillary functions" in the context of education refers to the tasks that teachers carry out that are not specifically related to teaching in the classroom, such as serving as class advisers, subject coordinators, club advisers, sports coaches, coordinators of both co-curricular and extracurricular activities, and community engagement services. Teachers do not perform actual teaching, yet these services are vital for the school's daily operations.

This implies that the teachers are carrying out administrative tasks, a situation hidden from the lenses of the typical metrics, which can compromise teaching quality (David et al., 2019).

In the 21st century, some aspects of public education are altered. These include the role of the school principal, which has undergone a significant transformation. When it comes to leadership, what was originally thought of as a boss-like position has evolved into that of a "facilitator of instructors," where the conventional subordination and isolation model has been replaced with collaboration and consensus building (Rosenblatt, 2004). Principals are providing opportunities for teachers to become more involved with new initiatives and responsibilities.

Usually, a person accepts many ancillary duties to advance their career (Parham & Gordon, 2011). However, there is more to that. Teachers who perform various ancillary duties significantly benefit their professional and personal growth. Additionally, it has broader implications for all of the educators in the country. Although they were given a more extensive range of teaching-related tasks, they used it as a guide to enhance their abilities and solidify their organization's dedication to public service. They were able to recognize the value of time management and that improving students' academic performance is one of their primary roles as teachers (Into & Gempes, 2018).

In the Philippines, the Department of Education (Dep Ed) schools are facing issues on how to meet the critical factors which bear significance in enhancing quality education. Variables, such as overlapping tasks and co-curricular activities of teachers, are reported as factors that hinder quality education in the country as cited by (Jackson, Schwab, & Schuler, 1986).

This support is provided in accordance with the teachers' areas of expertise. As experienced teachers have the confidence to decline when these functions are offered to them, it is inevitable that these functions are also given to new teachers the school leaders. In other cases, regardless of whether they have the necessary skills, these positions are offered to people who have lesser teaching loads. In the 21st century, some aspects of public education are altered. These include the role of the school principal, which has undergone a significant transformation. When it comes to leadership, what was originally thought of as a boss-like position has evolved into that of

a "facilitator of instructors," where the conventional subordination and isolation model has been replaced with collaboration and consensus building (Rosenblatt, 2004). Principals are providing opportunities for teachers to become more involved with new initiatives and responsibilities.

Usually, a person accepts many ancillary duties to advance their career (Parham & Gordon, 2011). However, there is more to that. Teachers who perform various ancillary duties significantly benefit their professional and personal growth. Additionally, it has broader implications for all of the educators in the country. Although they were given a more extensive range of teaching-related tasks, they used it as a guide to enhance their abilities and solidify their organization's dedication to public service. They were able to recognize the value of time management and that improving students' academic performance is one of their primary roles as teachers (Into & Gempes, 2018).

Multifaceted Curricular

In the study of Zickar, Gibby, Jenny (2004), they stated "role conflict" for teachers with multifaceted ancillary function happens if the primary and secondary jobs are very dissimilar. An employee is more likely to face role conflict and feel less satisfied, since more efforts are required to shift among the different roles and to adapt roles and behaviors to the different job demands.

To prevent outcomes of excessive stress of teachers, administrators need to be proactive and assist in managing the workload while, at the same time, foster collaborative responsibility and ownership (Don, Puteh, Nasir, Ashaari, & Kawangit, 2016; Martin, 1992).

However, on the study conducted by Sappa, Boldrini, and Aprea (2015), multifaceted ancillary functions were perceived by the teachers as a factor supporting their well-being. At the emotional level, combining teaching with another ancillary function seemed to support teachers in stepping back from situations encountered at school and keeping problems in perspective. In addition, being engaged in different professional activities was described as a source of strength and a way to remain continuously stimulated by different inputs. At the instructional level, various advantages were associated with the opportunity to multifaceted ancillary functions of teaching, since they experience stronger credibility in front of the students.

Extra-Curricular Activities of Teachers

Extra-curricular activities are programs and events carrying no academic credits organized by the designated school moderator together with students to showcase their interest and abilities, subject to direction and supervision of school. Educational process is not only confined inside the classroom but also outside the school. This is truly a learning process since it is not only confined inside the classroom (Retubada, 2014).

In the light of this type of education, teachers recognize the value of extra-curricular activities. To them, the major aim of these activities is to stimulate and develop the habits of engaging in worthwhile personality building and leisure time experience. They are important because they make use of innate drives and urge students by directing these free activities along channels that are educationally worthwhile. They also unify the school together with their colleagues and foster the spirit of cooperation and commitment building (Le Cornu & Ewing, 2008).

Nowadays, teachers are participating in day-to-day decision making in schools working side-by-side to set priorities, and dealing with organizational problems that affect their students' learning (Jordan, 2013). He added that many teachers also spend time researching various questions of educational effectiveness that expand the understanding of the dynamics of learning. More teachers are spending time mentoring new members of their profession, making sure that education school graduates are truly ready for the complex challenges of today's classrooms.

Meanwhile, under DepED Memorandum No. 291 dated June 13, 2008, the general guidelines for the implementation of the six hours of actual classroom teaching of public elementary and secondary teachers and the specific guidelines to be formulated at the school level for the remaining two hours to complete the eight hours of work, have been promulgated. The six hours of actual classroom teaching shall cover the full teaching load of a teacher as indicated in the class program. Teaching loads including advisorships and/or special assignments for the entire school year combined shall be considered as one teaching load. As cited in the memorandum, the special assignments of teacher as grade level coordinator, school paper adviser, class adviser, and property custodian for one actual teaching load.

However, the article published by Pearson, Carroll, and Hall (1994) mentioned that teachers who were empowered by the school were crossing the lines into managerial roles but were not being compensated for their increased responsibilities.

It was further revealed in the study entitled Relationships and Resilience: A Role for School Principal that when teachers experienced difficulties in their personal relationships, these difficulties were caused by their tiredness and a lack of energy due to multiple works load or ancillary functions (Peters & Pearce, 2012).

Ancillary functions are defined as engagements that provide vital support to the primary activities or operation of an organization and system. The ancillary functions among the teachers are operationally defined as that aside from their being classroom teachers; they have other school related functions, such as being designated as grade level advisers, subject coordinators/chairs, club moderators, coaches in sports, in-charge in co-curricular and extracurricular activities and community involvement services.

In other countries, like in Indonesia, ancillary services are embedded in the schools to support the implementation of the first four national standards of education regarding the national goal of education. In the Philippine context, these ancillary functions are provided according to the expertise of the teachers. However, it could not be avoided that these functions are also given to teachers upon entry, as experienced teachers have the confidence to decline when these functions are given to them. In other instances, these functions are given to those who have lesser teaching loads, regardless if they have the expertise or not. Digging into the basics to explain why people behave in a certain manner is a theory of motivation (Jones, 1959).

As Jones (1959) cited by Dweck (2013) has pointed out, the motivation theory attempts to explain “how behavior started, how could it be energized, sustained, directed, stopped, and the subjective reaction is felt by the organism. The theory of motivation that will be used to understand the effects of job design is Expectancy Theory, firmly adhered to by Georgopoulos, Mahoney, and Jones (1957) and Vroom (1964).

The theory of motivation being used to understand the effects of job design is the expectancy theory. This theory presupposed that the motivation of employees to perform effectively is determined by two variables. Firstly, it is contained in the concept of an effort-reward probability. Such is the person’s subjective probability that eventually directs an amount of effort to perform effectively will happen when given a reward or positively valued outcome. This effort-reward probability is measured by two subsection subjective probabilities. These are the probability that effort will result in performance and the probability that performance will result in the reward.

In 1964, Vroom refers to the first of these subjective probabilities as expectancy and to the second as an instrumentality. The second variable that is relevant here is the concept of reward value or valence.

Although most expectancy theories do not specify why certain outcomes have reward value, for the purpose of this study, the researchers argue that the reward value of outcomes stems from their perceived ability to satisfy one or more needs. Specifically, noteworthy here is the list of needs suggested by Maslow that includes security needs, social needs, esteem needs, and self-actualization needs. The evidence indicates that, for a given reward, reward value and the effort-reward probability combine multiplicatively to determine an individual’s motivation. This means that if either is low or nonexistent, then no motivation will be present. The present conceptualization of the interaction between job characteristics and individual differences is based primarily on the expectancy theory of motivation, as formulated by Lewin (1938) and Tolman (1959).

Expanding on the theory of Hackman and Lawler (1971), they proposed that jobs that offered the opportunity for satisfaction of higher-order needs (e.g., needs for personal growth and development or for the feeling of worthwhile accomplishment) should be associated with high levels of performance, satisfaction, and motivation and with low levels of absenteeism. They stated that to establish conditions for internal work motivation, then, it appears that a job must: (a) allow workers to feel responsible for an identifiable and meaningful portion of work, (b) provide outcomes which are intrinsically meaningful or otherwise experienced as worthwhile, and (c) provide feedback about performance effectiveness. Hence, this proposition validates the importance of assessment in the classroom performance of teachers as the second variable in this particular study.

As presented by Firestone (1991), Job Enlargement can be defined as utilizing “horizontal” skills or multiple ancillary functions that require skills that are at a similar level of complexity and responsibility. In teaching, it may consist of creating an additional workload aside from the regular task given.

Research on the offshoot of job enlargement programs shows that motivation is increased when additional tasks are interdependent (Wong & Campion, 1991). It was also added that job enlargement is directly related to high satisfaction (Campion & McClelland, 1993).

The recent recognition of these motivational problems has led management away from a specialization focus in the design of jobs toward an employment philosophy based on eliciting intrinsic reward from International Peer Reviewed Journal 61 work effort. Such incentives as feelings of self-worth, accomplishment, and pleasure from using and developing one’s skills are termed “intrinsic rewards” since they stem directly from work performance and are mediated or administered by the worker. A contrasting incentive locus is an external reward, for example, pay, job security, fringe benefits, etc., which are a function of the job situation and are given by others. This change in management thrust followed the analysis of Karlin and McGregor (1960).

However, it has been observed that teachers who the school empowered were crossing the lines into managerial roles but were not being compensated for their increased responsibilities (Pearson, Carroll, & Hall, 1994).

It was further noticed that when teachers experienced difficulties in their personal relationships, these difficulties were caused by their tiredness and a lack of energy due to multiple workloads or ancillary functions (Peters & Pearce, 2012).

Extracurricular activities are programs and events carrying no academic credits organized by the designated school moderator together with students to showcase their interests and abilities, subject to direction and supervision of the school. The educational process is not only coined inside the classroom but also outside the school. This is truly a learning process since it is not only coined inside the classroom (Retubada, 2014).

Interdependence among tasks on Ancillary Functions seems logically related to various motivational job design features. For example, when the outputs of several tasks are the inputs of other tasks, there may be higher intrinsic job feedback. That is, the quality of performance on some tasks is likely to be indicated when their output is needed to perform other tasks. Interdependent tasks may require more coordination and thus involve activities such as planning, scheduling, and inspecting, which may increase variety and skill usage. Autonomy may increase because coordinating tasks require the worker to decide among different schedules or ways of completing all the tasks. It is a matter of planning stage as well as the scheduling of activities that are imperative for success (Aldag, Barr, & Brief, 1981).

Methodology

Research Design

The descriptive correlation design of research was used to gather data on the multifaceted ancillary functions and work performance among public elementary school teachers in Buluan District, Division of Maguindanao-1, MBHTE, BARMM.

Respondents

This study used complete enumeration (Schoen, Eendebak and Nguyen, 2009) of public elementary school teachers in Buluan District, Division of Maguindanao-1, MBHTE-BARMM.

This study was conducted among public teachers in nine public elementary schools of Buluan District, Division of Maguindanao-1, MBHTE, BARMM.

Table 1. *Respondents of the study*

No.	Name of School	Sample (n)
1	Lower Siling ES	14
2	Datu Powa K. Mangudadatu ES	5
3	Maslabeng ES	12
4	Talitay ES	12
5	Popol ES	15
6	Bai Bagongan ES	14
7	Datu Yussef ES	5
8	Maguindanao Childhood Development Center	13
9	Datu Idoun ES	12
Total		102

Instrument

Survey questionnaire was used as a tool for the data collection. Questions included in the questionnaire were the teachers' multifaceted ancillary and work performance. The instrument for the study was validated by experts and tested for internal consistency using the Cronbach Alpha.

Procedure

The researcher asked permission from the district supervisor of the schools to collect data from the respondents. The researcher distributes the survey questionnaires that contained an informed consent form to each respondent in the school. At the day of data collection, the respondents were requested to sign the letter of consent, which was specified in the instrument for their voluntary participation of the study. Only those who signed the consent letter were considered as part of this study.

Participants were assured that their responses are kept confidential and that their names did not appear in any part of this study. After the data were retrieved, encoding of the data with proper label was carried out.

The participants were given time to complete the instruments. After they completed the instruments, they were asked to give the instruments to the school principal. The researcher individually retrieved the instruments from the principals of each school.

Data Analysis

The data gathered was statistically treated. As stated by CFI (2015), the mean computation was used to determine the extent of multifaceted ancillary functions and level of work performances of public elementary school teachers in Buluan District, Division of Maguindanao-1, MBHTE-BARMM. The correlation and regression analysis were employed to determine the relationship of the variables.

Ethical Considerations

This study followed ethical requirements. Respondents freely participated. Care was taken to assure their safety and well-being: being, and those they had no physical, mental, social, or emotional impairment. There was always respect for the school head. Participants include stakeholders. The privacy of the information obtained.

Results and Discussion

Extent of the Teachers' Multifaceted Ancillary Functions in Terms of Curricular Functions

Table 2 shows the grand mean of 4.37 described fully evident which shows the extent of multifaceted ancillary functions among public elementary school teachers in Buluan District in terms of curricular.

This result implies that teachers' have high demands in performing their roles as a teacher in the curriculum process to help students develop an engaged relationship with the content. Active learning will increase the focus and retention of the curriculum, resulting in an exciting learning environment. Teachers build lessons that include simulations, experiments, case studies and activities to deliver curriculum.

Moreover, the highest mean of 4.54 described the item fully evident which means teachers are likely to participate in maintaining and improving the school facilities that will help the teacher to be more productive and the students to be more interactive in the teaching-learning process.

On the other hand, the lowest mean of 4.18 described evident which shows that research, seminars, and workshops are also part of teachers' ancillary functions in terms of their curricular role.

In the study of Zickar et al. (2004), they stated "role conflict" for teachers with multifaceted ancillary functions happens if the primary and secondary jobs are very dissimilar. An employee is more likely to face role conflict and feel less satisfied, since more efforts are required to shift among the different roles and to adapt roles and behaviors to the different job demands. To prevent outcomes of excessive stress of teachers, administrators need to be proactive and assist in managing the workload while, at the same time, foster collaborative responsibility and ownership (Don, Puteh, Nasir, Ashaari, & Kawangit, 2016; Martin, 1992).

Table 2. Mean Score of the Teachers' Multifaceted Ancillary Functions in Terms of Curricular Functions

Indicators		Mean	Description
1.	Lesson Planning/Rubrics/Action and Work Plan/Evaluation & Assessment Tools	4.48	Fully Evident
2.	Preparation/Checking/Recording	4.49	Fully Evident
3.	Research/Seminars/Workshops	4.18	Evident
4.	Counseling/Mentoring/Coaching	4.20	Evident
5.	Home Visits/consultation and conference with Parent	4.28	Fully Evident
6.	Coordination Activities and Community Social Services	4.20	Evident
7.	Participation in the Maintenance and Improvement of School Facilities	4.54	Fully Evident
8.	Plus School's Unique Condition	4.38	Fully Evident
9.	Counseling/ Guidance	4.30	Fully Evident
10.	Class reports preparation	4.44	Fully Evident
11.	Organizer/ Supervision class activities	4.39	Fully Evident
12.	Special Assignments (ie. Learning Area Coordinator, Paper Adviser, Grade Chairman)	4.51	Fully Evident
Grand Mean		4.37	Fully Evident

Extend of the Teachers' Multifaceted Ancillary Functions in Terms of Extra-Curricular Functions.

Table 3 shows the grand mean of 4.27 described fully evident which shows the extent of multifaceted ancillary functions among public elementary teachers in Buluan District in terms of extra-curricular function.

This result implies that teachers were assigned with other school-related functions such as being designated as grade level advisers, subject coordinators/chairs, club moderators, coaches in sports, in-charge in co-curricular and extracurricular activities and community involvement services. Moreover, teachers are assigned in many functions.

Table 3. Mean Score of the Teachers' Multifaceted Ancillary Functions in Terms of Extra-Curricular Functions

Indicators		Mean	Description
1.	SBM (SIP/AIP)	4.45	Fully Evident
2.	Brigada/DRRM	4.48	Fully Evident
3.	Feeding /Gulayan	4.42	Fully Evident
4.	School Canteen	3.42	Evident
5.	Sports and other Event Competitions	4.04	Evident
6.	Learning Area Coordinators	4.49	Fully Evident
7.	EBEIS and LIS Coordinator	4.38	Fully Evident
8.	Health Assessment and 4Ps updating of Attendance	4.42	Fully Evident
9.	Others (various coordinator ship)	4.31	Fully Evident
Grand Mean		4.27	Fully Evident

The highest mean of 4.49 indicates that most of the teachers are assigned as Learning Area Coordinators in their respective school. However, the lowest mean with 3.42 described as evident means that teachers have also other function such as school canteen.

On the study conducted by Sappa, Boldrini, and Aprea (2015), multifaceted ancillary functions were perceived by the teachers as a factor supporting their well-being. At the emotional level, combining teaching with another ancillary function seemed to support teachers in stepping back from situations encountered at school and keeping problems in perspective.

Level of the Teachers' Work Performance in Terms of Instructional Planning.

Table 4 shows the grand mean of 4.55 and a description of outstanding which shows the level of teachers' work performance in terms of instructional planning.

This implies that the teachers have outstanding work performance in terms of instructional planning. Instructional planning and preparations are very important for the success of teachers' delivery of learning. Good teachers' skills in instructional will result to a good delivery of learning. The teachers were able to perform their duties effectively by having the appropriate and prescribed curriculum in teaching the learners.

The highest mean with 4.71 described as outstanding indicates that teachers have outstanding performance in choosing and preparing activities relevant to the prescribed curriculum. Additionally, the lowest mean of 4.41 with a description outstanding implies that teachers develop long-range plans and daily lessons.

Teaching is generally recognized as one of the most important and challenging occupations in contemporary society (Vesely, Saklofske & Leschied 2013). These professionals are regarded to be responsible for their students' academic achievement as well as social and emotional development (Elias and Arnold, 2006).

Table 4. Mean Score of the Teachers' Work Performance in Terms of Instructional Planning

Indicator		Mean	Description
<i>As a teacher, I...</i>			
1.	Follow prescribed curriculum	4.71	Outstanding
2.	Use available materials and resources	4.55	Outstanding
3.	Choose activities relevant to the prescribed curriculum	4.61	Outstanding
4.	Choose activities appropriate to student abilities	4.65	Outstanding
5.	Choose activities, materials, and resources appropriate for students with special needs	4.61	Outstanding
6.	Consider time available in planning	4.46	Outstanding
7.	Demonstrate flexibility in planning	4.48	Outstanding
8.	Plan student grouping according to instructional needs	4.51	Outstanding
9.	Develop long-range plans and daily lessons	4.41	Outstanding
Grand Mean		4.55	Outstanding

Level of Teachers' Work Performance in Terms of Involvement in Professional Growth Activities

Table 5 shows the grand mean of 4.54 and a description of outstanding which shows the level of teachers' work performance in terms of involvement in professional growth activities.

The teachers indicated that they have outstanding professional learning involvement. This is indicated by their participations in professional associations, participate on district/state committees, etc, participate in professional workshops, attend professional meetings, keep current in subject area, and engage in continuing education.

Table 5. Mean Score Teachers' Work Performance in Terms of Involvement in Professional Growth Activities

Indicator		Mean	Description
<i>As a teacher, I ...</i>			
1.	Am involved in professional associations	4.54	Outstanding
2.	Participate on district/state committees, etc	4.37	Outstanding
3.	Participate in professional workshops	4.55	Outstanding
4.	Attend professional meetings	4.55	Outstanding
5.	Keep current in subject area	4.59	Outstanding
6.	Engage in continuing education	4.65	Outstanding
Grand Mean		4.54	Outstanding

Moreover, the highest mean of 4.65 described outstanding engagement of teachers in continuing education. However, the lowest mean of 4.37 also described an outstanding participation of teachers in district or state relation activities.

This implies that the teachers have an outstanding performance in terms of their involvement in professional growth activities. Professional learning developments among teachers are very essential for enhancing their teaching skills. Teachers' continuing professional development is vital for a better pedagogical skills and knowledge.

As reported by Sedarmayanti [2009], the benefits of performance appraisal are performance improvement, competency adjustment, decision-making, personal placement, training needs and competency and skills development, career planning and development,

identification of deficiencies in the process of programming learning activities, opportunities, challenges from outside, and feedback for human resources.

Level of Teachers' Work Performance in Terms of Interaction with Administration and other Educational Personnel.

Table 6 shows the grand mean of 4.59 and a description of outstanding which shows the level of teachers' work performance in terms of interaction with administration and other educational personnel.

The highest mean of 4.63 described outstanding shows that teachers are having good working relationship with other teachers, administrators and other personnel. Additionally, the lowest mean of 4.55 with an outstanding description indicates that teachers have outstanding performance when it comes to informing administration and/or appropriate personnel of school related items.

In conclusion, the results implied that the teachers have been outstanding in interacting with administration and other educational personnel. The teachers manifested good working relations with their colleagues, supervisors, and with the community people. As indicated by Ainsworth, Smith and Millership [2008], some factors contributing to deterioration in teacher performance such as unsuitable performance plans goals; unclear performance plans, lack of knowledge or ability competence; and poor working conditions. Furthermore, performance is not defined by the action itself but by judgmental and evaluative processes (cf. Ilgen & Schneider, 1991; Motowidlo, Borman, & Schmit, 1997).

Table 6. *Teachers' Work Performance in Terms of Interaction with Administration and other Educational Personnel*

<i>As a teacher, I...</i>	<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Cooperate with other teachers, the administrators, and other educational personnel	4.61	Outstanding
2.	Make use of support services as needed	4.56	Outstanding
3.	Share ideas and methods with other teachers	4.58	Outstanding
4.	Inform administration and/or appropriate personnel of school related items	4.55	Outstanding
5.	Have good working relationship with other teachers, administrators and other personnel.	4.63	Outstanding
	Grand Mean	4.59	Outstanding

Level of Teachers' Work Performance in Terms of Interaction with Parents and Community

Table 7 shows the grand mean of 4.62 and described outstanding which shows the level of teachers' work performance in terms of interaction with parents and community.

This is indicated by encouraging community involvement with the school, provide a climate which opens up communication between the teacher and parent, communicates with parents in the best interest of the students, supports parent/teacher activities, and providing information related to support resources.

The highest mean of 4.70 and with a description outstanding implies that the teachers have an outstanding interaction with the parents and the community. Having a harmonious relationship is vital towards schools' success. Also, the lowest mean of 4.55 described outstanding result which shows that most of the teachers provide a climate which opens up communication between the teacher and parent, and provide information related to support resources.

As mentioned by Chisholm, Hoadley, Kivilu, Brooks, Prinsloo, Kgobe, Rule (2005), teacher performance is associated with the real time teachers spend for educational activities. The decrease in amount of time spent on teaching is caused by other duties such as school management, assessment and evaluation, and extracurricular activities.

Table 7. *Teachers' Work Performance in Terms of Interaction with Parents and Community*

<i>As a teacher, I ...</i>	<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Encourage community involvement with the school	4.70	Outstanding
2.	Provide a climate which opens up communication between the teacher and parent	4.55	Outstanding
3.	Communicate with parents in the best interest of the students	4.62	Outstanding
4.	Supports parent/teacher activities	4.69	Outstanding
5.	Provide information related to support resources	4.55	Outstanding
	Grand Mean	4.62	Outstanding

Level of Teachers' Work Performance in Terms of Providing Evaluative Feedback

Table 8 shows the grand mean of 4.49 and a description of outstanding which shows the level of teachers' work performance in terms of providing evaluative feedback.

The highest mean of 4.55 indicated an outstanding performance of the teachers when it comes to monitoring student progress through a variety of appropriate evaluation techniques. With the lowest mean of 4.42, teachers also shows outstanding result in prepare assignments which reflect the material which has been taught.

Overall, the results implied that the teachers are outstanding in providing evaluative feedback. In order for parents to monitor the academic success of their children, teachers must regularly give feedback to the parents on the success and difficulties of the learners. Reporting learners' progress to their parents is one of the best ways of meeting the academic needs of the learners. Ministry of National Education [2008], the tasks and responsibilities of teachers include (1) planning lessons, (2) delivering lessons (face-to-face), (3) assessing, (4) guiding students' activities, (5) doing additional works, and (6) developing the profession in education.

Table 8. *Teachers' Work Performance in Terms of Providing Evaluative Feedback*

Indicator		Mean	Description
<i>As a teacher, I...</i>			
1.	Make methods of evaluation clear and purposeful to learners	4.52	Outstanding
2.	Monitor student progress through a variety of appropriate evaluation techniques	4.55	Outstanding
3.	Prepare assignments which reflect the material which has been taught	4.42	Outstanding
4.	Provide feedback on assignments as quickly as possible	4.45	Outstanding
5.	Makes opportunities for one-to-one conferences to discuss learner's progress	4.49	Outstanding
6.	Interpret test results to learners and parents	4.52	Outstanding
Grand Mean		4.49	Outstanding

Level of Teachers' Work Performance in Terms of Supporting and Implementing School Regulations, Policies, Procedures and Accepted Practices

Table 9 shows the weighted mean of 4.47 and a description of outstanding which shows the level of teachers' work performance in terms of supporting and implementing school regulations, policies, procedures and accepted practices.

Additionally, the highest mean of 4.54 described outstanding results indicates that teachers are in adherence to authorized policies of the school. This is indicated by their support in the implementing school regulations, policies, procedures and accepted practices. With the lowest mean of 4.42, teachers also show an outstanding performance in participating in the development and review of school policies and regulations.

To sum up, the results implied that the teachers are outstanding in supporting and implementing school regulations, policies, procedures and accepted practices. A good teacher must abide the school rules and regulations. The teachers are abiding the school rules and regulations to avoid major errors in performing their duties and functions.

Numerous studies on individual work performance have been conducted. However, different approaches of studying individual work performance circulate in today's literature. Whereas the field of management has primarily occupied itself with how one can make an employee as productive as possible, the field of occupational health has focused on how to prevent productivity loss due to a certain disease or health impairment (Schultz, Chen, & Edington 2009; Halbeslebe, Wheeler, & Buckley, 2008).

Table 9. *Teachers' Work Performance in Terms of Supporting and Implementing School Regulations, Policies, Procedures and Accepted Practices*

Indicator		Mean	Description
<i>As a teacher, I....</i>			
1.	Adhere to authorized policies	4.48	Outstanding
2.	Select appropriate channels for resolving concerns/problems	4.45	Outstanding
3.	Participate in the development and review of school policies and regulations	4.42	Outstanding
4.	Strive to stay informed regarding policies and regulations applicable to his/her position	4.45	Outstanding
5.	Exercise responsibility for learner management throughout the entire building	4.54	Outstanding
6.	Use discretion in handling confidential information.	4.51	Outstanding
Grand Mean		4.47	Outstanding

Relationship between Teachers' Multifaceted Ancillary Functions and their Performance

Table 10 shows the relationship matrix between teachers' multifaceted ancillary functions and their performance.

Table 10. *Relationship between Teachers' Multifaceted Ancillary Functions and their Performance*

		<i>Instructional Planning</i>	<i>Involvement in Professional Growth Activities</i>	<i>Interaction with Administration and other Educational Personnel</i>	<i>Interaction with Parents and Community</i>	<i>Providing Evaluative Feedback</i>	<i>Supporting and Implementing School Regulations, Policies, Procedures and Accepted Practices</i>
Curricular Functions	Correlation Coefficient	.567**	.669**	.622**	.512**	.548**	.506**
	Sig.	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
Extra-Curricular Functions	Correlation Coefficient	.577**	.607**	.477**	.435**	.570**	.544**
	Sig.	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

** Highly significant

It reveals that all variables of teachers' multifaceted ancillary functions are significantly correlated with performance. This indicates that performance is highly dependent on teachers' multifaceted ancillary functions. Thus, fully evident performance of teachers' multifaceted ancillary functions will eventually result to an outstanding performance of work in the school.

The factors that influence performance, according to the partner-lawyer model proposed by Gibson, Ivancevich and Donnelly (2008), are expectations about rewards, encouragements, abilities, needs and traits, perceptions of tasks, internal and external rewards, perceptions of reward levels and job satisfaction.

Conclusions

Based on the result of the study, it can be concluded that the teachers have high demands of their multifaceted ancillary functions.

Interestingly, teachers have outstanding performance despite of their fully evident ancillary functions.

It can be also concluded that teachers' performance is highly dependent on their multifaceted ancillary functions.

Moreover, teachers' multifaceted functions are linked to their performance in the school in supporting and implementing school regulations, policies, procedures and accepted practices. Teachers with many functions tend to abide all school guidelines that make their performance outstanding.

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